

Challenges Associated with Overemphasis on Employee Resilience: Exploring Leadership Role and its Effect on Employee Well-being and Organisational Outcomes

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Resilience is regarded as a critical attribute to employee performance as it improves work-related outcomes in the face of adversity. However, there are unquestioned leadership practices that overemphasise individual resilience and often overlook consequences. The study had 2 objectives: first, to explore the challenges associated with the overemphasis on employee resilience; and second, to assess the consequences for employee well-being and organisational outcomes. The research was qualitative, and an interpretivist exploratory design was adopted. The sample consisted of ten participants, who were purposively sampled and interviewed. Data was thematically analysed. The analysis revealed that relying too heavily on resilience as a personal trait can obscure organisational responsibility, creating leadership gaps that harm the well-being of both employees and the organisation. Furthermore, the findings show unintended consequences such as burnout, higher attrition rates, and the neglect of systemic workplace issues. It is recommended that leadership practices be recalibrated to focus on transparency, emotional intelligence, and the cultivation of a supportive workplace environment. Resilience should be viewed as a shared organisational responsibility rather than an individual capability. The study's originality lies in its contribution to the broader discourse on sustainable leadership practices and in its practical insights for fostering resilience without compromising employee well-being. The findings guide the development of strategies to modify leadership practices, fostering a positive work environment where employees can flourish rather than just cope with workplace pressures.

Keywords: Leadership, resilience, employee resilience, psychological safety, well-being

Resilience is the capacity of individuals, teams, and organisations to withstand adversity, adapt positively to challenges, and ultimately thrive despite setbacks (Kuntz et al., 2017). In workplace environments, resilience is frequently viewed as a crucial trait for employees, enabling them to handle high-pressure situations, meet demanding expectations, and remain productive despite setbacks. Brady et al. (2025) and Hartmann et al. (2020) position resilience as a personal trait or resource that can be cultivated, enabling individuals to adapt positively to adversity. As a result, resilient individuals are better positioned to endure adversity and setbacks than their non-

resilient counterparts (Shin et al., 2012).

The business world is increasingly volatile, challenging and demanding, requiring employees to be more vigilant and rely on individual resilience. Srinivasan (2014) states that the work environment is continually evolving amid intensified competition and increasing complexity. Such working environments now require organisations to look for resilient employees who can adapt and flourish amid continuous change (Long et al., 2025). Resilience is often regarded as a personal strength that cultivates adaptive thoughts and behaviours and is a key to maintaining performance in the face of hardships (Grygorenko & Naydonova, 2023; Suslovic & Lett, 2024). Unfortunately, irresponsible leadership practices, such as impractical demands, unattainable workloads, insufficient support from management, and an obsessive focus on output (Jacobs, 2019) overwhelm employees with micromanagement. Resilience is seen as an aspect in the work environment that pushes employees to go the extra mile; however, without proper management and support, it derails the focus of employees.

Leaders often rely on employees' resilience, believing it can push them far and not seeing the negative effects of workplace stress (Hartwig et al., 2020). Chamorro-Premuzic and Lusk (2017) found that leaders' excessive reliance on resilience contributes to and worsens negative experiences in the workplace. Resilience is a measure of the ability to recover from severe trauma and hardship (Grygorenko & Naydonova, 2023). In the workplace, resilience is commensurate with how employees cope with stress, adapt to change, manage ambiguity and workplace conflict, navigate career

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transitions, and meet high expectations (Gallup, 2020). It is a leadership blind spot to think resilient employees are better equipped to contribute to collective goals. A culture of adaptability and perseverance needs to be fostered by organisational leadership (Northouse, 2021; Thompson et al., 2021). This is because excessive focus on resilience as a desirable employee trait has also led to stress-related challenges (Chamorro-Premuzic & Lusk, 2017) which have detrimental effects on employee well-being. While resilience is important, focusing too much on it to sustain employees can sometimes hide deeper structural and systemic issues that affect employees' well-being (Mahdiani & Ungar, 2021; Wut et al., 2022). Excessive emphasis on resilience leads leaders to inadvertently sustain unrealistic expectations, normalise excessive workloads, and diminish the importance of establishing supportive environments. The following sections of the article provide a background, a literature review, a methodology, findings, and a conclusion.

Background

Carmichael and Kumra (2022) agree with Lyytimäki et al. (2023) that resilience is an essential in high-performance industries. Leaders unknowingly use it to justify unsustainable goals. In South Africa, consulting firms often focus too much on resilience without addressing the root stressors, which may lead to increased disengagement and burnout (Swart, 2023). Leaders who fail to see resilience as an organisational responsibility perpetuate a culture in which employees are expected to endure adversity rather than offering them support, such as systemic reforms. The expectation that employees must "be resilient" obscures the role of leadership in creating healthier and more sustainable work environments.

The consulting industry is one of the rapidly evolving sectors due to technological advancements and demands that employees work on multiple projects with precision (Cerruti et al., 2019) without considering how stressful and overwhelming this can be for employees. The challenge lies in treating resilience as an individual trait rather than an element in the organisational support system. It becomes a leadership blind spot when they overlook systemic challenges such as excessive workloads and inadequate support structures, undermining employee well-being and sustainability (Fisher et al., 2024).

The consulting industry requires agile responses to clients' complex needs (Maddock, 2020). However, a culture of relentless performance expectations compels employees to work under tremendous stress, often to the detriment of their well-being. The consulting industry has an estimated global value of USD \$1 billion (The Business Research Company, 2024) and its demands can lead to burnout. Leaders tend to focus on employee resilience as a personal trait (Archer et al., 2024) rather than tackling systemic inefficiencies and often overlook their role in fostering a sustainable work environment.

High stress levels have been reported among employees in the consulting industry, with 45% reporting that the stressful work environment negatively affects their performance (Carmichael & Kumra, 2022). Due to the pace of technological advancement transforming workplaces and creating anxiety for employees, Gallup (2020) reports that only 15% of employees feel engaged at work, citing heavy workloads and insufficient support as the main reasons. On the one hand, the socio-economic instability and historical inequalities in South Africa exacerbate workplace stress and limit career mobility and workplace inclusion (Bester & Mabeka, 2024). On the other hand, leadership often misconstrues resilience in marginalised employees as an ability to endure and

thrive in difficult work environments, rather than recognising it as an indication that structural barriers must be addressed. (Walker, 2020). The study had a dual objective: to explore challenges associated with the overemphasis on employee resilience, and to assess the implications for employee well-being and organisational outcomes.

Review of Literature

Resilience in the Workplace

Resilience is a core construct of positive organisational behaviour (Hartmann et al., 2020; Luthans et al., 2002). Baker et al. (2021) state that resilience is both a personality trait and a dynamic process of positive adaptation in the face of adversity and change. Resilience is more than just coping and recovery; it is a successful adaptation tool and a form of psychological growth (Joseph, 2011). Moreover, it is intrinsically associated with well-being and positivity (Cooper et al., 2013; Tonkin et al., 2018). Resilience is also considered an indicator of life satisfaction (Mak et al., 2011), a personal resource for coping with stress (Robertson et al., 2015), and an enabler of effective social connections in resilient individuals (Brady et al., 2025). It is one of the key psychological capital resources (Luthans et al., 2015), associated with the ability to endure challenging conditions (King et al., 2016), which leads to positive adaptation (Hartwig et al., 2020). Resilience is among the most promising personal resources for coping with stress (Robertson et al., 2015).

Kuntz et al. (2017) state that emotional stability, perseverance, and the ability to adapt to changing circumstances are encapsulated in resilience. Further resilience in the workplace refers to an individual's ability to operate under pressure and handle setbacks without external intervention. Hence, the importance of leaders in establishing a conducive environment. This understanding highlights that resilience is not just a natural individual trait, but a rich, multifaceted competency influenced by the system of interrelationships (Southwick et al., 2014). Therefore, the interconnectedness among supportive leadership, organisational culture, and resource access is important in either promoting or inhibiting resilience (Bakker et al., 2023; Schwartz & Severson, 2023). This broader perspective indicates the importance of considering environmental and contextual influences alongside individual attributes for an employee to be resilient.

The Role of Leadership in Managing Resilience

Hartmann et al. (2020) found that many researchers have explored the link between leadership styles, the promotion of resilience and conducive environments. Positive organisational environments foster positive emotions, which in turn promote resilience (Malik & Garg, 2017). Transformational leadership, for instance, was found to enhance employees' positive affect that promotes resilience (Sommer et al., 2016). Northouse (2021) states that transformational leadership builds resilience through influence, motivation, stimulation, and individualised consideration. It is the responsibility of leaders to address the employees' needs by creating a positive organisational climate, managing dynamics with empathy, and fostering shared purpose. Zeng et al. (2020) assert that conducive environments enable adaptability and psychological safety. Furthermore, leaders themselves exemplify resilience through their conduct (Van Zyl, 2014). Jerab and Mabrouk (2023) agree that leaders who maintain their composure in turmoil can face the challenges and adapt further, persevering to achieve the intended outcomes, thereby setting an aspirational standard for their teams.

This resilience modelling reinforces credibility and provides a tangible benchmark for employees, who may look to their leaders as exemplars of adaptive and proactive behaviours (Edelmann et al., 2023; Schaubroeck et al., 2016).

Resilience is not only an innate characteristic but can also be developed and shared among organisational members through relational and behavioural interactions (McColl-Kennedy et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2022). When leaders visibly embody resilience, they contribute to building a resilient organisational culture, one in which employees are inspired and empowered to emulate similar behaviours (Afsar & Umrani, 2020). This reciprocal process of modelling and replication fosters collective resilience, enabling organisations to navigate uncertainties and challenges more effectively while maintaining cohesion and performance standards (Schaubroeck et al., 2021). This approach highlights leadership as an important link between individual and collective resilience, underscoring the relationship between leadership practices and organisational outcomes (Northouse, 2021; Thompson et al., 2021). For organisations to genuinely foster resilience, leadership strategies must expand beyond individual traits to include structural and cultural reforms that prioritise equitable resource distribution, clear communication, and psychological safety (Rees et al., 2015).

Well-being and Psychological Safety

Lehtonen (2023) found that the conceptualisation of resilience often overlooks the deeper systemic challenges that significantly affect employee well-being. Clarke et al. (2025) found that employees who display high levels of well-being perform better and become more effective organisational citizens. Gau and Gu (2025) define employee well-being as a positive emotional state arising from employees' work experiences. Martela (2025) refers to well-being as the extent to which an employee experiences and functions positively in their work environment. This naturally fosters resilience and motivates employees to take on additional responsibilities, thereby influencing organisational outcomes. Clarke et al. (2025) state that a psychologically safe workplace promotes higher well-being by ensuring that employees feel comfortable. Leaders are an essential component in creating a psychologically safe work environment (Clarke et al., 2025). Psychological safety positively relates to employee well-being, thereby positively impacting organisational outcomes (Tan, 2024).

Leaders who cultivate psychological safety clear hurdles for employees to reach full potential. The three concepts of leadership, psychological safety, and well-being converge to boost resilience, as leadership fosters a psychologically safe environment that promotes employee well-being, which, in turn, impacts resilience. However, structural problems such as chronic understaffing, unfair workload distribution, and unclear performance expectations remain persistent obstacles to resilience. Engetou (2017) state that employees frequently face challenges without organisational support, which increases stress and reduces their ability to recover and adapt effectively. Furthermore, overemphasising individual resilience may impede the leadership's ability to shape workplace experiences. While resilient individuals can temporarily buffer organisational inefficiencies, reliance on personal coping mechanisms often leads to burnout and attrition (Lyytimäki et al., 2023). This disproportionate focus on personal resilience creates a narrative that reinforces the tendency to place the burden of overcoming systemic issues solely on employees, perpetuating a

cycle of unrealistic expectations and neglecting the necessity for systemic accountability (Afsar & Umrani, 2020).

Method

The research adopted a qualitative exploratory design. Creswell and Poth (2016) state that qualitative research offers a holistic understanding of phenomena, allowing for flexibility in the design as new insights are gathered. Further, Creswell and Creswell (2022) agree that qualitative methodology is well-suited for exploring social and human constructs. The exploratory design enabled the researchers to interrogate the lived experience of resilience pressure in the consultancy business.

Participants

Ten participants were purposively sampled and interviewed. The participants were drawn from a consulting company with offices in six African countries. The inclusion criterion was that participants had worked in the consulting industry for at least 1.5 years. Purposive sampling ensured that the selected participants had experienced resilience pressure and could provide relevant data to help satisfy the two research objectives. Consent was sought for both participation and recording prior to the interviews, and the average interview length was 40 minutes. The interviews were semi-structured, allowing flexibility and subjective responses that led to additional themes to emerge (Buys et al., 2022). An interview guide containing probing questions was created to help organise and streamline the interviewing process (Collis & Hussey, 2014). Some of the questions covered the following topics:

- Can you identify and elaborate on common misconceptions about resilience in the workplace?
- From your perspective, how is resilience being used as a scapegoat for unaddressed challenges in the workplace?
- What leadership style do you think can foster resilience?
- To what extent do you think leaders in the organisation are equipped to nurture resilience?
- How do you think leadership influences employees' ability to bounce back from setbacks and challenges?
- How can leaders inspire and empower their team members to embrace change and adapt to challenging circumstances?
- What opportunities can organisations leverage to ensure leaders nurture and harness individual and organisational resilience?

Table 1 below profiles the participants.

Table 1

Participant Profile

Participant Number	Gender	Years of Experience
P1	Female	5
P2	Female	8
P3	Female	8
P4	Male	10
P5	Female	8
P6	Female	8
P7	Male	6
P8	Male	8
P9	Female	1.5
P10	Male	4

Note. Author's Own Compilation

To maintain confidentiality and safeguard the participants' privacy, all identifying information was anonymised, and coded identifiers, such as P1, P2, and so forth, were used to refer to each participant as shown in Table 1. The anonymisation process was carefully designed to protect the participants' identities. Data was analysed using Braun and Clarke's (2023) thematic analysis framework to facilitate the identification of recurring themes and patterns across the data.

Table 2*Example of Colour Coding*

Transcription from Participant showing codes in colour	Sub-themes
"I think some employees believe that all or most consulting firms expect an unfair level of resilience from their employees... resilience	Misconceptions about resilience
So, consulting has a somewhat negative reputation in that, in some circles, it's perceived as being too extractive and too demanding, in terms of how resilient people can or should be....."	Unfair levels of resilience
"So, that's a misconception I feel about the expectation of resilience, particularly in consulting....." "	Misconceptions about resilience
They put you in situations with undue pressure, tight timelines, and unreasonable clients because it's expected of you to be resilient". "	Workplace stress
In my experience, not all consulting firms understand resilience and its implications for the quality of an employee's work well-being	Effect on psychological well-being

Codes of similar colour were combined to create sub-themes, which, in turn, merged into themes based on common attributes. This article focused on one of the six themes identified during the analysis, specifically the theme related to leadership practices that promote resilience. In line with Braun and Clarke (2023) the final step of thematic analysis is the presentation of findings, which was done through a narrative approach (Toendepi, 2017). Direct quotes from participants were used to support the themes, thereby grounding the findings in the data (Wang & Geale, 2015). Narratives convey and interpret participants' perspectives by carefully integrating them into a coherent whole (Michelon et al., 2022). A narrative offers a systemic framework to the presentation of findings (Braun & Clarke, 2023). At the same time, the intricate nuances of the participants' experiences are preserved, while simultaneously aligning with and fulfilling the overarching research objectives (Mills et al., 2012; Toendepi, 2017).

Procedure

Participation was voluntary. Participants were informed of the study's purpose, and consent was obtained verbally and in writing. Participants could withdraw at any time without consequences, as was outlined in the consent forms and elaborated on during the introduction to the interviewing process. The rights of all participants were outlined before the interviews began. To further protect participants, anonymity was maintained throughout the research using pseudonyms. Data was safeguarded in secure password-protected systems accessible to the researchers and will be retained in accordance with the institution's data management policy.

Results

Below in Table 3, the theme and its sub-themes are presented.

Analysis

The steps followed in the analysis were familiarisation with the data, generating initial codes, identifying themes, reviewing and refining these themes, assigning names to the themes, and ultimately composing the analytical write-up (Braun & Clarke, 2023). Table 2 below illustrates the 2nd step of data analysis, where a manual colour coding was used to highlight important, pertinent, and recurring codes (Kara & Toendepi, 2023).

Table 3*Themes and Sub-themes*

Theme	Sub-theme
Leadership practices that foster resilience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Being a model citizen ● Cultivating psychological safety ● Knowledge sharing and continuous feedback ● Practising individualised consideration for employees

Note. Authors' Own Compilation

Theme: Leadership Practices that Foster Resilience

For long-term sustainability, organisations need to have resilient employees who can sustain performance during the volatile environments that are prevailing. Effective leaders empower their teams to adapt with agility. Key leadership practices, such as leading by example, fostering psychological safety, encouraging knowledge sharing, providing continuous feedback, and offering individualised consideration, are critical to fostering resilience.

Sub-theme 1: Being a Model Citizen

Effective leaders are role models as they display commensurate behaviours and practices in the workplace. Employees usually emulate and imitate their leaders' behaviours, whether ethical or not. Leaders who demonstrate good leadership practices have a positive impact on organisational culture as employees adopt similar values and behaviours in their own work. The participants reiterated that where leadership "walk-the-talk" and set exemplary behaviour, it creates positive vibes in the organisation that stimulates resilience during trauma, stressful events or uncertainty.

"One should lead by example. So, I think there is a difference between saying, yes, we support wellness, we support this, versus, like, embodying that and living that yourself." P6.

"You really need to be an example, because you are literally the first source of experience that employees are getting right." P10

Leadership behaviour was identified as a key factor in fostering both employee and organisational resilience.

"I don't even know if this is a leadership style per se, but I actually think, like, leaders who are willing to model positivity themselves". P1

"It's the example that's set. ...The way that my leader has walked the talk in terms of prioritising a worklife balance, healthy boundaries at work, and being excited about things. So really setting an example has modelled that for me and made me realise it's okay to have a worklife balance and to be excited about something, challenge myself in a new way, or step out in a way that maybe I could fail because that space is created for me to do that, and I feel safe. Yeah, safe to do that, and to speak openly when I disagree". P5

A leader who demonstrates transparency, fairness, and a willingness to be non-hierarchical can also instil confidence and positive emotions in employees. Participants observed that witnessing their leader exerting comparable effort on the job fostered a sense of safety and support.

"The reason why I can push on and like work until very late on Friday morning and not feel like I am being mistreated or I'm being exploited in my job is that I know my leader is doing the same." P8

Leaders who prioritise work-life balance, establish healthy boundaries, and demonstrate enthusiasm for challenges foster an environment where employees feel secure in taking risks and are encouraged to openly discuss their personal struggles.

Sub-theme 2: Cultivating Psychological Safety

Psychological safety is essential for fostering resilience within teams, as it allows employees to express their concerns without fear of judgment or reprisal. Leaders who foster a culture of psychological safety enable open communication and help alleviate fears about work challenges.

"Maybe the biggest one is, like, holding a safe space... To me, I think the way I'm defining that safe space is, again, like, knowing that I can be my full self, and that I will be judged fairly." P1

"My first thought was that it's about responding to and alleviating people's fears... there's like a level of threatening precarity there that isn't there in other kinds of relationships." P6

Positive relations in the organisation were also singled out as key to fostering resilience.

"A leader who is attentive and prioritises actually listening to what you're saying is something that helps foster resilience because you don't feel like you're alone. I think a primary factor in feeling resilient is a sense of community". P9

"So, whether it's in going through tough times, where you might be like, let go of. You know there's still consideration for who you are, what you want to do, and how you move forward, even if you have to go through a change in the company. It's like, 'Who are you and what do you want to do?'" P3

Leaders who live by and consistently demonstrate their values can

further support their teams, with one participant noting that value-driven leadership is a powerful tool for cultivating resilience.

"So, these are your personal values, and you really believe in them. And the way that you live your life, do your work, engage with people, engage with colleagues... can equip you to be a leader that fosters resilience." P8

Psychological safety is an important enabler and facilitator of the leader-follower relationship.

"I think it's leadership creating a space of safety, where you feel like you can voice your needs, where you can, like, voice your concerns and issues, and not be judged or penalised for it is massive" P5

There is an urgent need for leaders to be proactive and intentional in fostering psychological safety in the workplace. Doing so creates a supportive and enabling environment, which in turn strengthens team cohesion and productivity.

"Psychological safety looks like you not only saying, 'whenever you have an issue, you can come to talk to me', but proactively saying, 'Hey, it looks like something is going on. Do you want to talk about it?'" P7

"I think of Leader A, who says, 'Come talk to me when you have an issue, and Leader B, who says, 'Hey, I see your morale has been down. Can we talk about it?'" I think those are two different things. Because one gives you the confidence to come to them to talk about it. It also gives you the impression that I am interested in hearing about the challenges that you are facing. The former sounds like a tick box, where, you know, it's the right thing to say. It is, therefore, about being open to listening and genuinely interested in people's success. ... especially transformational leaders, are interested in your well-being, they are interested in your potential, and they want to see you reach it". P7

A good relationship with employees, where leaders genuinely care for others and frequently check in on them, cultivates psychological safety.

"..in that case, it would need to be frequent touch bases, maybe weekly or bi-weekly. Within those meetings, there should be a designated component where the leader asks the employee how they are doing. 'What are the things that you need to get done? And how can I assist you in completing these additional tasks? If you need assistance, what resources can I mobilise to make sure that you're able to meet your tasks?'" P4

Psychological safety promotes empathy in the workplace, and such an enabling environment creates a sense that allows employees to express their thoughts freely without fear of harsh criticism or judgment.

"I would also say that providing an enabling environment and consideration of those who are working, I think that's important. Even a light touch human aspect of genuinely being considerate towards what another person is going through. And trying to understand that". P4

"Again, I think empathy is sort of like holding that really safe space that says, 'I see you, and I'm here for you, and I'm gonna cheer you on no matter what'. ...It's that whole aspect of putting people before processes, and I don't know what the other piece is, but I think it's like those leaders that really do truly put people first in the actions, not just in the words". P1

"Empathy and the human approach to relationships within the

team bring resilience. I think that has been critical: people feel seen, people feel heard, they feel it's a safe place, and there is empathy for actual life beyond work. ...People are more willing to participate in tough times because there's support, there's a human connection side". P5

Participants noted the importance of psychological safety through shared experiences.

"I think there's something really shared in group trauma, you know. Some of the friends that I'm the closest with are people I was retrenched alongside. And we might share cackles about like, 'oh, remember that time, and when this happened?'. But those are some of the solid friendships that I've formed. And mentorships, as well, are people I still lean on". P3

"Experiences that people can share, for example, because if we can share an experience together, it fosters a team spirit". P8

Sub-theme 3: Knowledge Sharing and Continuous Feedback

Knowledge sharing and ongoing feedback are crucial for building resilience, as they equip employees with the resources and guidance to handle challenges more effectively. Leaders who share their own experiences and lessons learnt from past difficulties can empower employees to succeed and learn from others.

"I always find that very empowering when it comes from leaders. When they say, 'I remember when I was in your role, and I remember when I first managed another junior team member, or I remember when I had to do feedback... when they put themselves in your shoes and go back, but they're also unafraid to say, 'I was there too, I struggled with ABCD. And here's how I overcame it.'" P1

It involves taking the learnings from own experiences and sharing them with others". P3

"...the qualities that I think foster resilience are being a proactive leader. A leader who is very much open to engaging with the challenges that you are experiencing on the project and helping you model or identify resources within the organisation that you can lean on. ... then the leader helps facilitate your understanding of how to manage the stresses and challenges you are encountering". P9

"How you handle situations where people make mistakes. How you correct people, so to speak? How you give people feedback, particularly in instances where the feedback is maybe harsh or serious? Yeah, those are the behaviours that are productive for fostering resilience". P8

Learning opportunities for developing resilience can be easily gained through training and development, such as leadership coaching or mentoring.

"I would love some coaching to help me transition into this correctly". P3

"So my department's mentorship is a good example of how to help employees manage their resilience effectively. Because you have someone else who's been there before you or worked the journey alongside you, and they're not part of your team". P8

When leaders are unaware of their employees' upskilling needs, regular, constructive feedback is crucial for professional career growth. Hence, ongoing feedback was highlighted as an important 'temperature check' for employees to gauge the organisation's status.

"Resilience is probably best fostered in environments where a leader is able to communicate, is able to provide feedback, is able to focus on the long-term picture while being flexible and also is able to move away from strict and rigid processes and approaches that don't allow for human autonomy". P4

"I think line managers as well as leaders are going to be key for that feedback mechanism to let people know that they're on the right track, or not on the right track. ...So, a leader who understands both the policy and the human nuances would be able to make a more accurate call in terms of providing helpful feedback, growth-driven feedback, rather than punitive feedback". P4

"I think the firm does a decent job of this with the 360 upward feedback situations, as well as the [DEI] survey. ... that captures the views of junior team members adequately about leadership and how leadership is affecting the workplace". P8

Sub-theme 4: Practising Individualised Consideration

Individualised consideration is a vital leadership practice that acknowledges each employee's unique strengths, needs, and aspirations. While cultivating individualised relationships with employees, leaders can provide tailored support that promotes resilience in both personal and professional spheres.

"Taking the time to get to know your employees is really important...I think that helps with knowing what someone might need or notand having a relationship." P6

"I think it's when the leadership is tailored to the individuals, and there's a way you can measure, and you can see that they're moving closer to their potential". P2

Authenticity and mindfulness in leadership, along with individualised consideration, are essential for fostering trust and respect. When leaders genuinely care about their actions and their impact on employees, they foster core values of loyalty and security within their teams. This, in turn, encourages individuals to follow and support those leaders.

"... Incredibly supportive of people's careers. he will take the time to sit with people, really understand them and think about how to equip them. ...He invests in that in a meaningful way". P6

"You want to know that you can trust leadership and that leadership has your trust. And that, you know, we're in this together. That no one is trying to exploit you. Your voice matters. And that over and above the work, your leaders care about you as a person, as a human being. So, it requires a certain level of authenticity from the leadership". P8

Creating an enabling environment goes beyond addressing individual needs; it also involves fostering a culture of positive behaviour and supporting its practice.

"Providing an enabling environment and consideration for those who are working is important. Even a light touch of a genuinely considerate human aspect towards what another person is going through. And trying to understand that". P4

"Perhaps one of the most significant ones is to allow employees to present themselves as individuals. I think let people show up. Let people come as they are. Especially because we have passed the screening". P1

Discussion

This study had a dual objective of exploring the overemphasis on

employee resilience and assessing its implications for employee well-being and organisational outcomes. The findings are centred around leadership behaviour, indicating that leaders tend to overlook profound systemic challenges within the organisation that affect employee well-being, often scapegoating a lack of employee resilience. Overemphasising resilience as an individual trait is a leadership blind spot, particularly because inadequate leader support, micromanagement, poorly articulated work outputs, and inequitable workloads affect employees' and organisational well-being. Jacobs (2019) identifies excessive workloads and impractical work demands as key sources of workplace stress. Leaders were reported to underestimate their responsibility to serve as exemplars of resilience and to tailor support in ways that effectively promote resilience in both personal and professional development. The findings indicate that demands for resilience often conceal unrealistic expectations, which participants identified as a key leadership blind spot. The findings show that leaders are not being proactive in modelling leadership resilience to reinforce credibility and provide tangible benchmarks for employees who look up to them.

Jerab and Mabrouk (2023) argue that leaders who remain calm in the face of adversity are better able to adapt to challenges and persist in achieving their goals, thereby setting an inspirational example for their employees. Furthermore, Northouse (2021) states that building resilience through influence and individualised consideration fosters a positive work environment. Hence, resilience must be seen as extending beyond individual traits to include structural and cultural reforms that prioritise the equitable distribution of resources, clear communication, and psychological safety (Rees et al., 2015).

These findings suggest that leader behaviour is crucial for fostering resilience, as leaders set an example by demonstrating their own resilience in the workplace. Afsar and Umrani (2020) found that leaders who embody resilience encourage employees to do the same. Schaubroeck et al. (2021) concur, arguing that replicating modelling processes fosters collective resilience. This study found that leaders are responsible for nurturing a resilient atmosphere in the organisation by creating a psychologically safe, enabling work environment, which enhances employee well-being and organisational outcomes. Since resilience, leadership, psychological safety, and well-being are closely interconnected, effective leadership fosters psychological safety, which in turn enhances employee well-being and strengthens resilience.

The interconnected relationship positions leadership as the foundational mechanism through which a psychologically safe work environment is established, characterised by positivity, individualised consideration, knowledge sharing, and trust. Psychological safety acts as a means to enhance employee well-being when there are positive leader relations, well-defined job characteristics, and a conducive working environment (Frazier et al., 2017). Enhanced well-being, in turn, facilitates the development of employee psychological resilience, as reflected in individuals' capacity to adapt, cope with, and recover from workplace challenges and adversity. A reinforced feedback loop comes into effect when increased resilience supports psychological safety by building confidence, activating proactive actions, and building reciprocal relations in the workplace. Collectively, these dynamic interactions sustain employee performance and drive organisational outcomes.

Conclusion

Excessive reliance on resilience can both enable and exacerbate

negative experiences in the workplace. Individual and organisational well-being are affected by this phenomenon of overestimating employee resilience. As resilience is essential in navigating workplace challenges, it cannot be achieved without intentional leadership practices that create supportive environments. Irresponsible leadership practices that overburden employees with insufficient support structures on the ground overstretch employees. Yet it is the responsibility of leaders to foster resilience by modelling ethical behaviour, creating psychologically safe environments, encouraging knowledge sharing, and providing personalised support. Such practices empower employees to thrive in the face of adversity and enhance collective responsibility and adaptability within the organisation. Recognising and addressing these hidden costs is essential for building workplaces that strike a balance between high performance and employee well-being, ultimately driving long-term success and sustainability. The findings are important for developing strategies to adjust leadership practices and promote healthier environments that empower employees to thrive rather than merely endure workplace pressures.

References

- Afsar, B., & Umrani, W.A. (2020). Transformational leadership and innovative work behaviour: The role of motivation to learn, task complexity, and innovation climate. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 23(3), 402-428. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJIM-12-2018-0257>.
- Baker, F.R., Baker, K.L., & Burrell, J. (2021). Introducing the skills-based model of personal resilience: Drawing on content and process factors to build resilience in the workplace. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 94(2), 458-481. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joop.12340>.
- Bakker, A.B., Hetland, J., Olsen, O.K., & Espevik, R. (2023). Daily transformational leadership: A source of inspiration for follower performance. *European Management Journal*, 41, 700-708. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emj.2022.04.004>.
- Bester, K., & Mabeka, N. (2024). *South African economic trends and workplace mental health: Employer-employee responsibilities*. Available at: <https://www.derebus.org.za/south-african-economic-trends-and-workplace-mental-health-employer-employee-responsibilities/> (Accessed: 12 February 2025).
- Brady, J.M., Hammer, L.B., & Westman, M. (2025). Supervisor resilience promotes employee well-being: The role of resource crossover. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 156, 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2024.104076>.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2023). Toward good practice in thematic analysis: Avoiding common problems and becoming a knowing researcher. *International Journal of Transgender Health*, 24(1), 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.1080/26895269.2022.2129597>.
- Burnard, P., Gill, P., Stewart, K., Treasure, E., & Chadwick, B. (2008). Analysing and presenting qualitative data. *British Dental Journal*, 204, 429-432. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.bdj.2008.292>.
- Buys, T., Casteleijn, D., & Untiedt, H. (2022). A reflexive lens on preparing and conducting semi-structured interviews with academic colleagues. *Qualitative Health Research*, 32(13), 2030-2039. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10497323221130832>.
- Carmichael, A., & Kumra, G. (2022). *Building a mentally resilient workforce*. Available at: <https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/future-of-asia/future-of-asia-podcasts/building-a-mentally-resilient-workforce> (Accessed: 29 February 2025).
- Cerruti, C., Tavoletti, E., & Grieco, C. (2019). Management consulting: A review of fifty years of scholarly research. *Management Research Review*, 42(8), 902-925. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MRR-03-2018-0100>.
- Chamorro-Premuzic, T., & Lusk, D. (2017). The dark side of resilience. *Harvard Business Review*, 16, 1-4.
- Clarke, E., Näswall, K., Masselot, A., & Malinen, S. (2025). Feeling safe to speak up: Leaders improving employee well-being through psychological safety. *Economic and Industrial Democracy*, 46(1), 152-176. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0143831X231226303>.
- Collis, J., & Hussey, R. (2014). *Business research: A practical guide for undergraduate and postgraduate students*. 4th edn. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Cooper, C.L., Flint-Taylor, J., & Pearn, M. (2013). *Building resilience for success: A resource for managers and organizations*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan. <https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137367839>.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2022). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (6th ed.). Sage.
- Creswell, J. W., & Poth, C. N. (2016). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches*. Sage.

- Edelmann, C.M., Boen, F., Stouten, J., Van den Broeck, G., & Fransen, K. (2023). The power of peer leaders: Exploring the link between peer leadership behaviors and sustainable work outcomes. *Behavioral Sciences, 12*(2), 1-38. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs14010002>.
- Engetou, M.E. (2017). *Impact of insufficient personnel on organizational performance*. Centria University of Applied Sciences.
- Fisher, J., Affaf, S., Fields, A., & Comisso, C. (2024). *Is a covering culture undermining your organization's well-being efforts?* Available at: <https://www2.deloitte.com/us/en/insights/topics/talent/identity-covering-could-be-undermining-workplace-well-being-efforts.html> (Accessed: December 2024).
- Gallup (2020). *Employee engagement*. Available at: <https://www.gallup.com/394373/indicator-employee-engagement.aspx> (Accessed: 2 May 2024).
- Gao, H., & Gu, Q. (2025). Does leader stewardship behavior affect employee creativity? Roles of other orientation and employee well-being. *Personnel Review, 55*(1), 310-329. <https://doi.org/10.1108/PR-07-2024-0652>.
- Grygorenko, Z., & Naydonova, G. (2023). The concept of resilience: History of formation and approaches to definition. *Public Administration and Law Review, 2*(14), 76-88. <https://doi.org/10.36690/2674-5216-2023-2-76-88>.
- Hartmann, S., Weiss, M., Newman, A., & Hoegl, M. (2020). Resilience in the workplace: A multilevel review and synthesis. *Applied Psychology, 69*(3), 913-959. <https://doi.org/10.1111/apps.12191>.
- Hartwig, A., Clarke, S., Johnson, S., & Willis, S. (2020). Workplace team resilience. *Organizational Psychology Review, 10*(3), 169-200. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2041386620919476>.
- Ibrahim, B.A., & Hussein, S.M. (2024). Relationship between resilience at work, work engagement and job satisfaction among engineers: A cross-sectional study. *BMC Public Health, 24*(1), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-024-18507-9>.
- Jacobs, C.M. (2019). Ineffective-leader-induced occupational stress. *SAGE Open, 9*(2), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244019855858>.
- Jerab, D., & Mabrouk, T. (2023). The role of leadership in changing organizational culture. *SSRN Electronic Journal, 1*-13. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4574324>.
- Joseph, S. (2011). *What doesn't kill us: A guide to overcoming adversity and moving forward*. London: Hachette.
- Kara, I., & Toendepi, J. (2023). *Accommodative leadership: Understanding the behavioural aspects of Affirmationals in a South African work context*. Social Sciences International Research Conference (SSIRC) 2023, 1013 October, Durban, South Africa. Available at: <https://commerce.nwu.ac.za/social-sciences-international-research-conference/ssirc-2023> (Accessed: December 2023).
- King, D.D., Newman, A., & Luthans, F. (2016). Not if, but when we need resilience in the workplace. *Journal of Organizational Behavior, 37*(5), 782-786. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.2063>.
- Kuntz, J.C. (2021). Resilience in times of global pandemic: Steering recovery and thriving trajectories. *Applied Psychology, 70*(1), 188-215. <https://doi.org/10.1111/apps.12296>.
- Lehtonen, P. (2023). *Measuring systemic factors is key to improving workplace performance*. Available at: <https://www.flowtrace.co/collaboration-blog/measuring-systemic-factors-is-key-to-improving-workplace-performance> (Accessed: 29 May 2024).
- Long, T., Cooke, F.L., & Mavondo, F. (2025). Developing a resilient workforce in the context of organisational change: The role of employee assistance programmes. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management, 36*(9), 1592-1620. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2025.245828>.
- Luthans, F. (2002). Positive organizational behavior: Developing and managing psychological strengths. *Academy of Management Perspectives, 16*(1), 57-72. <https://doi.org/10.5465/ame.2002.6640181>.
- Luthans, F., Youssef-Morgan, C.M., & Avolio, B.J. (2015). *Psychological capital and beyond*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Lyytimäki, J., Teperi, A.M., Jylha, K.M., da Silva Vieira, R., & Mervala, E. (2023). Dark side of resilience: Systemic unsustainability. *Frontiers in Sustainability, 1*-5. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsus.2023.1241553>.
- Mahdiani, H., & Ungar, M. (2021). The dark side of resilience. *Adversity and Resilience Science, 2*, 147-155. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42844-021-00031-z>.
- Mak, W.W., Ng, I.S., & Wong, C.C. (2011). Resilience: enhancing well-being through the positive cognitive triad. *Journal of Counselling Psychology, 58*(4), 610-617. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0025195>.
- Martela, F. (2025). Well-being as having, loving, doing, and being: An integrative organising framework for employee well-being. *Journal of Organizational Behavior, 46*(5), 641-661. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.2862>.
- McColl-Kennedy, J.R., Breidbach, C.F., Green, T., Zaki, M., Gain, A.M., & van Driel, M.L. (2023). Cultivating resilience for sustainable service ecosystems in turbulent times: Evidence from primary healthcare. *Journal of Services Marketing, 37*(9), 1167-1185. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSM-03-2023-0100>.
- Michelon, G., Trojanowski, G., & Sealy, R. (2022). Narrative reporting: State of the art and future challenges. *Accounting in Europe, 19*(1), 7-47.
- Mills, A.J., Durepos, G., & Wiebe, E. (2012). Thematic analysis. In A. Mills, G. Durepos, and E. Wiebe (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of case study research* (pp. 926-927). Newbury Park, CA: Sage Publications. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412957397>.
- Northouse, P.G. (2021). *Leadership: Theory and practice*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE.
- Rees, C.S., Breen, L.J., Cusack, L., & Hegney, D. (2015). Understanding individual resilience in the workplace: The international collaboration of workforce resilience model. *Psychology for Clinical Settings, 6*(73), 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2015.00073>.
- Robertson, I.T., Cooper, C.L., Sarkar, M., & Curran, T. (2015). Resilience training in the workplace from 2003 to 2014: A systematic review. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology, 88*(3), 533-562. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joop.12120>.
- Schaubroeck, J.M., Lam, S.S., & Peng, A.C. (2016). Can peers' ethical and transformational leadership improve co-workers' service quality? A latent growth analysis. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes, 133*, 45-58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.obhdp.2016.02.002>.
- Schwartz, T., & Severson, E. (2023). *Why we glorify overwork and refuse to rest*. Available at: <https://hbr.org/2023/08/why-we-glorify-overwork-and-refuse-to-rest> (Accessed: September 2024).
- Shin, J., Taylor, M.S., & Seo, M.G. (2012). Resources for change: The relationships of organizational inducements and psychological resilience to employees' attitudes and behaviors toward organizational change. *Academy of Management Journal, 55*(3), 727-748. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amj.2010.0325>.
- Sommer, S.A., Howell, J.M., & Hadley, C.N. (2016). Keeping positive and building strength: The role of affect and team leadership in developing resilience during an organizational crisis. *Group and Organization Management, 41*(2), 172-202. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1059601115578027>.
- Southwick, S.M., Bonanno, G.A., Masten, A.S., Panter-Brick, C., & Yehuda, R. (2014). Resilience definitions, theory, and challenges: Interdisciplinary perspectives. *European Journal of Psychotraumatology, 5*(1), 1-14.
- Srinivasan, R. (2014). The management consulting industry growth of consulting services in India: Panel discussion. *IIMB: Management Review, 26*(4), 257-270. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iimb.2014.09.001>.
- Suslovic, B., & Lett, E. (2024). Resilience is an adverse event: A critical discussion of resilience theory in health services research and public health. *Community Health Equity Research and Policy, 44*(3), 339-343. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2752535X231159721>.
- Swart, J. (2023). *Resilience can be a double-edged sword*. Available at: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/resilience-can-double-edged-sword-joan-swart> (Accessed: 11 July 2025).
- Tan, C. (2024). Beyond emotional intelligence: A re-conceptualisation of resonant leadership. *Philosophy of Management, 23*(4), 421-437. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40926-024-00315-1>.
- The Business Research Company (2024). *Management consulting services global market report 2024*. Available at: <https://www.thebusinessresearchcompany.com/report/management-consulting-services-global-market-report> (Accessed: May 2025).
- Thompson, G., Buch, R., & Glas, L. (2021). The impact of transformational leadership and interactional justice on follower performance and organizational commitment in a business context. *Journal of General Management, 46*(4), 274-283. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0306307020984579>.
- Toendepi, J. (2017). *Transformational leadership as a catalyst to higher levels of consciousness in social systems*. [Unpublished master's thesis]. University of Johannesburg. Available at: <https://hdl.handle.net/10210/237821>.
- Tonkin, K., Malinen, S., Näswall, K., & Kuntz, J.C. (2018). Building employee resilience through well-being in organizations. *Human Resource Development Quarterly, 29*, 107-124. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hrdq.21306>.
- van Zyl, E. (2014). The role of self-leadership in becoming an ethical leader in the South African work context. *African Journal of Business Ethics, 8*(2), 5-14.
- Walker, R. (2020). *Minorities in consulting how to overcome workplace barriers*. Available at: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/johnkotter/2020/02/11/minorities-in-consulting-how-to-overcome-workplace-barriers/> (Accessed: 17 July 2024).
- Wang, C.C., & Geale, S. (2015). The power of story: Narrative inquiry as a methodology in nursing research. *International Journal of Nursing Sciences, 2*(2), 195-198.
- Wut, T.M., Lee, S.W., & Xu, J. (2022). Role of organizational resilience and psychological resilience in the workplace integral stakeholder perspective. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 19*(18), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph191811799>.
- Zeng, H., Zhao, L., & Zhao, Y. (2020). Inclusive leadership and taking-charge behaviour: Roles of psychological safety and thriving at work. *Frontiers in Psychology, 11*(62), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00062>.
- Zhang, N., Yang, S., & Jia, P. (2022). Cultivating resilience during the COVID-19 pandemic: A socioecological perspective. *Annual Review of Psychology, 73*, 575-598. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-030221-031857>.

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